

The effect of administering a combination of vitamin D3 and vitamin E (α -tocopherol) in sepsis rats induced by *Staphylococcus aureus*

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Received 16 June 2025 ♦ Accepted 26 September 2025 ♦ Published 21 October 2025

Citation: Bangun P, Rusip G, Mutia MS, Handayani P (2025) The effect of administering a combination of vitamin D3 and vitamin E (α -tocopherol) in sepsis rats induced by *Staphylococcus aureus*. Pharmacia 72: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e162155>

Abstract

This study investigated the therapeutic effectiveness of the combination of vitamin D3 and vitamin E in a sepsis rat model. Thirty-five male Wistar rats were categorized into seven groups: normal, negative, and positive controls (doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW), and four treatment groups administered vitamin D3 (36, 72, or 144 IU/kg BW) in conjunction with vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW), with or without doxycycline. Rats were injected with *Staphylococcus aureus* (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL), followed by a 7-day oral therapy. The combined therapy, particularly at elevated doses (72 and 144 IU/kg BW), significantly reduced leukocyte counts and inflammatory biomarkers (TNF- α , IL-6, procalcitonin, and CRP) compared to the untreated group ($p < 0.05$). Liver enzymes and renal function indicators also decreased markedly, indicating a reduction in organ failure. The findings indicate that high-dose vitamin D3 and vitamin E provide significant immunomodulatory and organ-protective benefits in sepsis, reinforcing their potential as adjuvant therapies.

Keywords

rat, sepsis, *Staphylococcus aureus*, vitamin D3, vitamin E

Introduction

Sepsis is a complex and lethal condition arising from an over-vigorous and dysregulated immune response to infection. If not promptly managed, this excessive reaction leads to systemic inflammation, tissue damage, and ultimately multi-organ failure (Srivastava and Singh 2024). Sepsis continues to account for a significant proportion of morbidity and mortality globally among hospitalized patients. It impacts individuals across all age groups, with the highest recorded risk among the elderly, infants, and individuals with compromised immune systems (Martín et al. 2017).

The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that sepsis results in millions of fatalities annually, a significant portion of which might be prevented via prompt diagnosis and effective therapeutic interventions (La Via et al. 2024).

Staphylococcus aureus is among the most prevalent and virulent pathogens associated with sepsis. This Gram-positive bacterium is a significant factor in the onset of severe sepsis and septic shock, and it predominantly causes skin and soft tissue infections (Jin et al. 2021). Its pathogenicity is attributed to its ability to evade host immune defenses and produce several toxins, resulting in persistent inflammation and tissue necrosis (Ahmad-Mansour et al. 2021).

Complications such as disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) – which significantly elevate mortality risk – can result from the systemic dissemination of *S. aureus*.

The pathophysiology of sepsis is characterized by a sequence of immune responses triggered by the invading pathogen. Pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) on immune cells initially detect microbial components, triggering signaling pathways that generate pro-inflammatory cytokines such as tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) (Xu et al. 2025). This initially beneficial cytokine storm can become detrimental over time, leading to capillary leakage, hypotension, reduced oxygen transport to tissues, and endothelial dysfunction. Clinical indicators of sepsis progression frequently include hematological and biochemical alterations such as elevated leukocyte count, hyperglycemia, increased procalcitonin (PCT), and C-reactive protein (CRP).

Recent data indicate that micronutrients, particularly vitamins with immunomodulatory and antioxidant properties, may assist in regulating the immune response during sepsis. Historically linked to calcium-phosphate equilibrium and skeletal health, vitamin D3, or cholecalciferol, is now recognized as a significant regulator of both innate and adaptive immunity (Bellavia et al. 2024). It enhances the microbial killing capacity of monocytes and facilitates their differentiation into macrophages. Moreover, vitamin D3 enhances anti-inflammatory mediators while inhibiting the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines, thus preserving immunological homeostasis. Decreased vitamin D3 levels have been associated with increased susceptibility to infections and poorer outcomes in critically ill patients, especially those with sepsis (Lang and Aspinall 2017).

Vitamin E, particularly in the form of α -tocopherol, is a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant that neutralizes reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby protecting cell membranes from oxidative damage (Kilicarslan et al. 2024). Excessive reactive oxygen species production during sepsis surpasses the body's inherent antioxidant defenses, resulting in oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, and cellular apoptosis. Vitamin E has been shown to reduce oxidative damage and enhance the function of immune cells, including natural killer (NK) cells and T lymphocytes, in multiple organs (Li et al. 2024). These attributes suggest a potential role for vitamin E in mitigating the oxidative burden and immunological dysfunction associated with sepsis.

While numerous studies have examined the individual effects of vitamin D3 and vitamin E in sepsis and other inflammatory illnesses, there has been less research on their combined impact. Their co-administration is rational due to their distinct yet complementary mechanisms of action: vitamin E primarily addresses oxidative damage, whereas vitamin D3 influences immune responses and inflammation. Consequently, a combinatorial effect can enhance host defense mechanisms, diminish inflammatory dam-

age, and more effectively preserve organ function compared to each vitamin alone. This study aims to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of combining vitamin D3 and vitamin E in a rat model of sepsis induced by *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Staphylococcus aureus* was administered intraperitoneally to induce sepsis; the subjects received treatment 7 days post-induction. Leukocyte counts, pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6), procalcitonin (PCT), C-reactive protein (CRP), liver enzymes (SGOT, SGPT), and renal indicators (creatinine, urea) were measured.

Materials and methods

Materials

The materials used in this study included male Wistar rats, *Staphylococcus aureus* strain (ATCC 25293), nutrient agar, Petri dishes, disposable 1 mL syringes, a spectrophotometer, McFarland turbidity standard (0.5), an automated hematology analyzer, a glucometer, sterile saline solution, disposable gloves, animal housing cages, and water bottles. The ELISA kits used were for TNF- α , IL-6, procalcitonin (PCT), and C-reactive protein (CRP) (Solarbio, China). Biochemical test kits were used for SGOT, SGPT, creatinine, and urea (DiaSys Diagnostic Systems, Germany). Vitamin D3 (cholecalciferol) and vitamin E (α -tocopherol) were obtained in the generic product.

Animal preparation

The experiment involved 35 male Wistar rats, each weighing between 250 and 300 g. All rats were maintained under standardized conditions, including a 12-hour light–dark cycle, controlled room temperature (22 ± 2 °C), and unrestricted access to water and standard rodent feed. Ethical clearance for this study was granted by the Laboratory Animal Research Ethics Committee of Universitas Prima Indonesia (Approval No: 044/KEPK/UNPRI/X/2024).

Staphylococcus aureus bacterial inoculum preparation

The *Staphylococcus aureus* strain (ATCC 25293) was sourced from the American Type Culture Collection. The bacteria were cultured on nutrient agar and incubated at 37 °C for 18–20 hours. A suspension was then prepared using physiological saline, and its turbidity was adjusted to match the 0.5 McFarland standard (equivalent to 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL) using a spectrophotometer at 600 nm. Each rat was subsequently administered 1 mL of the suspension intraperitoneally [11].

Experimental design

The animals were randomly assigned to seven experimental groups, with five rats in each group ($n = 5$). Each group received a specific treatment as follows:

- a. Group 1 (normal healthy control): Received no treatment and served as the baseline reference for physiological and biochemical parameters.
- b. Group 2 (negative control): Induced with *S. aureus* but received no therapeutic intervention.
- c. Group 3 (positive control): Induced with *S. aureus* and treated orally with doxycycline at a dose of 9 mg/kg BW/day.
- d. Group 4: Induced with *S. aureus* and treated orally with doxycycline (9 mg/kg BW/day) in combination with vitamin D3 (36 IU/kg BW/day) and vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW/day).
- e. Group 5: Induced with *S. aureus* and administered orally with vitamin D3 (36 IU/kg BW/day) and vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW/day).
- f. Group 6: Induced with *S. aureus* and administered orally with vitamin D3 (72 IU/kg BW/day) and vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW/day).
- g. Group 7: Induced with *S. aureus* and administered orally with vitamin D3 (144 IU/kg BW/day) and vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW/day).

All treatments were given once daily for seven consecutive days following sepsis induction. Vitamin E (α -tocopherol) was administered at a fixed dose of 250 mg/kg BW. This dosage was adapted from Atli et al. (2012), in which vitamin E was used in combination with selenium and demonstrated protective effects in sepsis-related lung injury. Although selenium was part of the original protocol, the current study selected the α -tocopherol dose alone in order to isolate its effect. This dose is within the non-toxic, pharmacologically active range reported in rodent models of oxidative injury and sepsis. This fixed dose allowed us to maintain a consistent antioxidant background while varying vitamin D3 levels to assess potential dose–response patterns. Future studies should include multiple vitamin E doses to optimize combination therapy. Moreover, doxycycline (9 mg/kg BW/day) was selected as the positive control based on its proven efficacy against *Staphylococcus aureus* in rodent sepsis models and its additional anti-inflammatory and anti-matrix metalloproteinase effects, which may mitigate sepsis-related tissue injury (de Oliveira and Miranda 2024). Its dual antimicrobial and host-response modulating actions provide a robust reference for evaluating the therapeutic potential of the vitamin D3 and vitamin E combination.

Induction of sepsis and treatment design

Sepsis was induced in rats via intraperitoneal injection of *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL (Zuelli et al. 2014). All groups designated for sepsis induction (Groups 2–7) received 1 mL of the bacterial suspension, whereas the healthy control group (Group 1) was administered 1 mL of sterile physiological saline as a placebo. Following a 48-hour post-infection period to allow sepsis to develop, treatment was initiated based on each group's respective regimen. This delayed-start ap-

proach was chosen to simulate a clinically relevant scenario in which therapeutic measures are applied after the onset of systemic infection rather than at the point of bacterial challenge. Such timing has been employed in previous sepsis studies to evaluate the efficacy of interventions under more advanced inflammatory conditions. Furthermore, treatments included oral administration of vitamin D3, vitamin E, doxycycline, or a combination thereof, given once daily for seven consecutive days.

All oral treatments were administered once daily using a sterile, ball-tipped stainless steel gavage needle attached to a calibrated syringe. The vitamin D3, vitamin E, and doxycycline solutions/suspensions were freshly prepared each day in an appropriate vehicle to achieve the target dose per kilogram of body weight. Each rat was gently restrained to minimize stress, and the gavage needle was carefully inserted into the esophagus to deliver the full calculated volume directly into the stomach. The needle was then withdrawn slowly to avoid regurgitation or aspiration, and animals were observed briefly after dosing to ensure normal behavior and swallowing.

Sample collection and analysis

Twenty-four hours after the final treatment, blood samples were collected from the inferior vena cava of each rat under anesthesia to minimize stress and ensure precision during sampling. Using sterile techniques and equipment, blood was carefully withdrawn with a syringe to avoid contamination. The samples were then subjected to hematological assessments, including complete blood count (CBC), and biochemical analyses (Usmani et al. 2023). Inflammatory biomarkers measured included TNF- α , IL-6, procalcitonin (PCT), and C-reactive protein (CRP) using the ELISA method (de Oliveira et al. 2015). Additionally, liver function markers (SGOT, SGPT, and albumin) and renal function markers (creatinine and urea) were evaluated to assess organ integrity following treatment (Al-Kadi et al. 2020).

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism 9.0 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Comparisons between groups were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant (Kim 2014).

Results and discussion

Blood bacterial culture

The outcomes of the blood bacterial culture across all experimental groups are shown in Fig. 1. The normal control group (A) exhibited no bacterial growth, consistent with the absence of infection. In contrast, the negative control

Figure 1. Blood bacterial culture: A. Normal; B. Negative control; C. Doxycycline; D. Doxycycline + vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; E. Vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; F. Vitamin D3 72 IU + vitamin E; G. Vitamin D3 144 IU + vitamin E.

group (B), which was induced with *Staphylococcus aureus* but received no treatment, showed dense bacterial colonies, confirming the successful induction of sepsis.

Remarkably, no bacterial growth was observed in any of the treatment groups, including the positive control (C, doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW), the combination therapy group (D, doxycycline + vitamin D3 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW), and all groups treated with vitamins D3 and E alone at varying doses (E–G). This indicates that both standard antibiotic therapy and vitamin-based interventions were effective in eliminating bacterial presence from the bloodstream.

The absence of bacterial colonies in vitamin D3- and E-treated groups suggests a significant antimicrobial effect, particularly at higher vitamin D3 doses. Vitamin D3 is known to upregulate antimicrobial peptides such as cathelicidin and defensins, which disrupt bacterial membranes and enhance immune clearance (White 2022). Additionally, vitamin E's antioxidant properties support immune function by protecting leukocytes from oxidative damage, thereby facilitating a more effective immune response (Hashem et al. 2021; Rusip et al. 2022). These findings are in agreement with previous studies reporting that vitamin D supplementation improves infection outcomes in sepsis (Quraishi et al. 2015), while Hartmann et al. (2020) highlighted the antibacterial and immunoprotective role of vitamin E. The comparable results between vitamin-only and doxycycline-treated groups suggest that vitamins D3 and E, especially in combination, could serve as potential adjunct therapies in bacterial sepsis management.

Leukocyte parameters

Leukocyte counts in the experimental groups are summarized in Table 1. The data reveal that the negative control

Table 1. Leukocyte count.

Groups	Leukocytes ($10^9/L$) \pm SD
Normal Group	$3.69 \pm 0.66^*$
Negative control (untreated sepsis group)	10.12 ± 1.60
Positive control (doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW)	$4.24 \pm 0.57^*$
Doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW + vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	$4.65 \pm 0.91^*$
Vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	$4.52 \pm 0.63^*$
Vitamin D 72 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	$4.46 \pm 0.82^*$
Vitamin D 144 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	$4.54 \pm 1.01^*$

Notes: * = significantly different from the negative control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

group (untreated sepsis group) exhibited a significant increase in leukocyte levels, indicating a robust inflammatory response following induction with *Staphylococcus aureus*. In contrast, all treated groups showed significantly reduced leukocyte counts compared to the negative control ($p \leq 0.05$), suggesting the effectiveness of both doxycycline and the vitamin-based interventions in suppressing inflammation. The normal control group had the lowest leukocyte count, reflecting baseline physiological conditions. The positive control group treated with doxycycline alone also showed a marked reduction, supporting the antibiotic's efficacy. Interestingly, the combination of doxycycline with vitamin D3 and vitamin E (Group D) yielded leukocyte levels comparable to those of the positive control, suggesting a potential synergistic effect.

Additionally, groups treated solely with vitamins D3 and E (Groups E–G) demonstrated a dose-dependent decrease in leukocyte counts, with the most notable reductions observed in the higher dose groups (72 and 144 IU/kg BW of vitamin D3). These findings suggest that vita-

mins D3 and E contribute to immunomodulation by reducing systemic inflammation.

From a theoretical standpoint, vitamin D3 is known to play a crucial role in modulating both innate and adaptive immune responses. These observations are supported by previous research. A study reported that vitamin D supplementation reduced leukocyte infiltration and systemic inflammation in a sepsis-induced animal model (Fajri 2024). Similarly, Traber and Atkinson (2007) demonstrated that vitamin E supplementation significantly improved immune response and reduced leukocyte activation in inflammatory conditions. The current findings are consistent with these results and further emphasize the potential of combining vitamins D3 and E as adjunctive therapies in the management of sepsis. Overall, the results indicate that vitamins D3 and E, particularly at higher doses, can significantly reduce leukocyte counts in septic rats, supporting their role as immunomodulatory agents. These findings highlight the potential utility of vitamin-based therapies in mitigating excessive inflammatory responses such as those seen in bacterial sepsis.

Liver and kidney function

The effects of treatment on liver and kidney function biomarkers are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. In the negative control group, which received *Staphylococcus aureus* without treatment, SGOT, SGPT, creatinine, and urea levels were significantly elevated, indicating hepatic and renal dysfunction resulting from sepsis-induced systemic inflammation and oxidative stress. In contrast, all treatment groups exhibited significantly reduced levels of these

biomarkers compared to the negative control ($p \leq 0.05$), suggesting both hepatoprotective and nephroprotective effects from the administered therapies.

The normal control group demonstrated the lowest levels across all parameters, reflecting baseline physiological function. The positive control group treated with doxycycline showed substantial improvement, with SGOT, SGPT, creatinine, and urea values nearing those of the healthy control, confirming the efficacy of antibiotic intervention in mitigating sepsis-associated organ injury.

Notably, groups receiving vitamin D3 and vitamin E, either in combination with doxycycline or as standalone therapy, showed consistent reductions in both liver and kidney injury markers. Among these, the groups receiving vitamin D3 at 72 IU/kg BW and 144 IU/kg BW, along with vitamin E, displayed levels that were significantly improved compared to the septic group and comparable to the positive control, indicating that higher doses may offer enhanced protection.

These results are supported by mechanistic insights into how sepsis impairs liver and kidney function. Vitamin E, a potent lipid-soluble antioxidant, protects cellular membranes from oxidative stress, particularly in metabolically active organs like the liver and kidneys (Fang et al. 2021; Podszun and Frank 2021). Consistent with our findings, a study by Seif and Abdelwahed (2014) demonstrated that vitamin D3 supplementation in rats reduced liver enzyme levels and histological damage. Similarly, Khatami et al. (2016) reported that vitamin E supplementation reduced serum creatinine and urea in oxidative injury models, indicating renal protection. These parallels strengthen the interpretation that vitamins D3 and E contribute to the

Table 2. Result of biochemical in liver function.

Groups	Serum SGOT (U/L) \pm SD	Serum SGPT (U/L) \pm SD
Normal group	134.4 \pm 3.97*	53.6 \pm 4.39*
Negative control (untreated sepsis group)	292.4 \pm 3.97	115.4 \pm 17.47
Positive control (doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW)	126.2 \pm 6.30*	42.6 \pm 5.03*
Doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW + vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	157 \pm 1.58*	49.2 \pm 18.07*
Vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	118.4 \pm 3.97*	72 \pm 6.28*
Vitamin D 72 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	153 \pm 14.88*	74.4 \pm 3.97*
Vitamin D 144 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	179.4 \pm 3.97*	67.8 \pm 8.41*

Notes: * = significantly different from the negative control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 3. Result of biochemical analysis in kidney function.

Groups	Creatinine (g/dL) \pm SD	Urea (g/dL) \pm SD
Normal group	0.85 \pm 0.04*	22.0 \pm 4.74*
Negative control (untreated sepsis group)	1.41 \pm 0.13	42.8 \pm 5.54
Positive control (doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW)	0.59 \pm 0.06*	23.4 \pm 5.32*
Doxycycline 9 mg/kg BW + vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	0.77 \pm 0.03*	19.2 \pm 5.72*
Vitamin D 36 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	0.61 \pm 0.02*	17.6 \pm 3.91*
Vitamin D 72 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	0.70 \pm 0.10*	20.4 \pm 6.88*
Vitamin D 144 IU/kg BW + vitamin E 250 mg/kg BW	0.70 \pm 0.10*	19 \pm 3.81*

Notes: * = significantly different from the negative control group ($p \leq 0.05$).

restoration of organ function in septic conditions. Taken together, the data suggest that vitamin D3 and vitamin E, particularly at higher doses, exert protective effects on liver and kidney function during sepsis. Their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties may complement standard antibiotic therapy, making them promising adjuncts for managing organ dysfunction in septic patients.

Histological evaluation of liver and lung tissues

Histological observations of liver and lung tissues across all experimental groups are illustrated in Figs 2, 3.

In the normal control group (Fig. 2A), hepatic histology appeared intact, with well-preserved lobular architecture and no signs of cellular degeneration or necrosis (score 0). The negative control group (Fig. 2B) exhibited severe liver damage (score 4), characterized by hydropic degeneration and hepatocellular necrosis – classic features of sepsis-induced hepatic injury due to systemic inflammation and oxidative stress. The positive control group treated with doxycycline alone (Fig. 2C) showed improved liver morphology with reduced damage, primarily parenchymatous degeneration (score 2), indicating partial restoration of hepatic integrity.

Treatment with vitamin D3 and vitamin E resulted in varying degrees of hepatic improvement. Groups receiving vitamin D3 at 36 IU/kg BW (Fig. 2E) and 144 IU/kg BW (Fig. 2G) showed histological scores of 2, reflecting moderate protection with only parenchymal degeneration. However, Group 6 (vitamin D3 72 IU/kg BW + vitamin E, Fig. 2F) displayed persistent hepatic injury with hydropic degeneration and necrosis, scoring 4, suggesting a potential threshold effect or inter-animal variability at this dose. The higher liver injury score in Group 6 may reflect inter-animal variability and small sample size effects. Notably, liver function biomarkers in this group still

improved compared to the negative control, supporting an overall treatment benefit.

The group receiving a combination of doxycycline and vitamins (Fig. 2D) also showed a score of 2, supporting a synergistic protective effect. These liver tissue findings align with the known mechanisms by which vitamin D3 suppresses NF- κ B-mediated inflammation and vitamin E neutralizes reactive oxygen species, thereby limiting hepatocellular injury during sepsis (Aboelez et al. 2024).

Lung histology from the normal group (Fig. 3A) displayed healthy alveolar structures with clear air spaces and no inflammation (score 0). Conversely, the negative control group (Fig. 3B) showed extensive lung damage (score 4), with alveolar swelling, interstitial hemorrhage, and infiltration of lymphocytes, consistent with acute lung injury from sepsis.

Notably, substantial improvements were observed in the lung tissues of groups treated with vitamins D3 and E. Groups 5–7 (Fig. 3E–G) all presented with reduced damage (score 2), evidenced by preserved alveolar spaces and reduced inflammatory infiltration, suggesting that these vitamins mitigate pulmonary inflammation. Group 3 (positive control, doxycycline only; Fig. 3C) also showed moderate improvements (score 2). Interestingly, Group 4 (doxycycline + vitamins; Fig. 3D) still exhibited severe lung injury (score 4), which may reflect variability in drug–tissue interaction or timing of response in pulmonary tissue compared to hepatic tissue. These results support previous findings that vitamins D3 and E can reduce inflammation and oxidative damage in sepsis models. Histopathological evaluations confirm that vitamin D3 and vitamin E, particularly at appropriate dosing levels, provide protective effects against sepsis-induced damage in both liver and lung tissues. The observed improvements in tissue structure support the combined use of these therapies as potential adjuncts to standard sepsis management, capable of mitigating systemic organ injury and improving clinical outcomes.

Figure 2. Histological evaluation of liver tissue: A. Normal; B. Negative control; C. Doxycycline; D. Doxycycline + vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; E. Vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; F. Vitamin D3 72 IU + vitamin E; G. Vitamin D3 144 IU + vitamin E.

Figure 3. Histological evaluation of lung tissue: A. Normal; B. Negative control; C. Doxycycline; D. Doxycycline + vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; E. Vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; F. Vitamin D3 72 IU + vitamin E; G. Vitamin D3 144 IU + vitamin E.

Evaluation of serum inflammatory cytokines

The levels of pro-inflammatory markers, including TNF- α , IL-6, CRP, and procalcitonin (PCT), across all experimental groups are shown in Fig. 4.

A pronounced elevation in all measured inflammatory cytokines – tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), interleukin-6 (IL-6), C-reactive protein (CRP), and procalcitonin (PCT) – was observed in the negative control group (Group 2), indicating a strong systemic inflammatory response following the induction of sepsis with *Staphylococcus aureus*. This cytokine surge is characteristic of the hyperinflammatory phase of sepsis, where uncontrolled release of pro-inflammatory mediators contributes to capillary leakage, tissue hypoxia, immune dysregulation, and ultimately multi-organ dysfunction. Elevated IL-6 and TNF- α , in particular, are known to play central roles in sepsis pathophysiology, initiating and amplifying the cascade of inflammatory events that compromise vascular integrity and organ function (Tang et al. 2024). CRP and PCT, commonly used clinical biomarkers for inflammation and infection severity, were also significantly raised in the negative control group, reinforcing the model's validity for mimicking the septic condition (Liang and Yu 2022).

In contrast, all treatment groups exhibited significant reductions in these inflammatory markers compared to the negative control ($p \leq 0.05$). This suggests that the interventions not only curtailed the systemic inflammatory response but also may have contributed to the restoration of immune homeostasis. Notably, the groups treated with combinations of vitamin D3 and vitamin E, particularly at higher doses (Groups 6 and 7, receiving 72 and 144 IU/kg BW of vitamin D3, respectively), demonstrated

the most substantial decreases in IL-6 and TNF- α levels. These findings highlight the dose-dependent anti-inflammatory potential of vitamin D3, supported by its known role in modulating the immune response through the inhibition of nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) signaling. NF- κ B is a transcription factor responsible for the expression of multiple pro-inflammatory genes. Vitamin D3, through the activation of the vitamin D receptor (VDR), downregulates this pathway, thereby reducing cytokine synthesis (Nimitphong et al. 2021).

Vitamin E, a lipid-soluble antioxidant, further contributes to inflammation attenuation by neutralizing reactive oxygen species (ROS), stabilizing cell membranes, and preserving leukocyte function during oxidative stress. ROS are known to potentiate cytokine production in sepsis, and their scavenging by vitamin E helps interrupt this feedforward loop (Sahoo et al. 2024). These mechanisms provide a biological rationale for the significant reductions in cytokine levels seen in the vitamin-treated groups.

The antibiotic-treated group (Group 3) also showed a meaningful reduction in all inflammatory markers compared to the negative control, underscoring the efficacy of doxycycline in combating bacterial infection and reducing infection-driven inflammation. Interestingly, Group 4, which received a combination of doxycycline, vitamin D3 (36 IU/kg BW), and vitamin E (250 mg/kg BW), displayed even lower cytokine levels in several markers compared to the antibiotic-only group, suggesting a synergistic interaction. This implies that while doxycycline addresses the microbial source of inflammation, vitamins D3 and E may support immunological recovery and limit inflammatory tissue damage.

These results are consistent with findings from prior studies. Several studies reported that vitamin D3 supple-

Figure 4. Cytokine marker levels: A. IL-6; B. TNF- α ; C. CRP; D. PCT across treatment groups. G1: normal; G2: negative control; G3: doxycycline; G4: doxycycline + vitamin D3 + vitamin E; G5: vitamin D3 36 IU + vitamin E; G6: vitamin D3 72 IU + vitamin E; G7: vitamin D3 144 IU + vitamin E.

mentation significantly reduced IL-6 and TNF- α levels in endotoxin-challenged mice by modulating T-cell and monocyte function (Han et al. 2019; Dang 2021). Likewise, Li et al. (2024) demonstrated that vitamin E lowered oxidative stress-induced cytokine production in macrophages, leading to a more regulated immune response. Clinical studies have also identified a correlation between low serum vitamin D levels and worse sepsis outcomes, suggesting its importance in immune regulation (Cutuli et al. 2024). Additionally, vitamin E has been shown to decrease CRP levels in patients with chronic inflammatory conditions, suggesting that its benefits extend beyond antioxidation to direct immunological modulation (Saboori et al. 2015). The present study adds to this body of evidence by demonstrating the combined benefit of vitamins D3 and E in an in vivo sepsis model. The significant reductions in CRP and PCT levels observed in Groups 6 and 7 further reinforce the systemic anti-inflammatory effect of these vitamins. Since hepatocytes produce CRP in response to IL-6, and PCT is a specific marker of bacterial infection and sepsis severity, their suppression indicates not only local immune regulation but also systemic recovery from septic insult.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the co-administration of vitamin D3 and vitamin E, particularly at higher doses, can modulate the immune response, suppress pro-inflammatory cytokine production, and reduce systemic markers of inflammation during sepsis. The data support the hypothesis that these vitamins have both immunoregulatory and organ-protective roles in the context of infectious inflammation. Their use as adjunctive therapy alongside antibiotics may offer a more comprehensive approach to managing sepsis by targeting both the microbial and inflammatory components of the disease. Future studies exploring the molecular mechanisms, optimal dosing, and potential clinical applications of these findings are warranted.

Limitation

The sample size of five animals per group was determined using Federer's formula. With seven treatment groups in this study, the formula indicated a minimum of four animals per group; we used five to improve precision while minimizing animal use in accordance with ethical standards. Nevertheless, the relatively small sample size may reduce statistical power. Additionally, although one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was applied to adjust for multiple pairwise comparisons, the number of endpoints tested warrants cautious interpretation, and results should be confirmed in larger, adequately powered studies with pre-specified primary outcomes. Finally, the lack of vitamin D3-only and vitamin E-only monotherapy groups was another limitation. Since the current design aimed to assess the combination strategy in a proof-of-concept study, the absence of single-agent arms precludes separating possible synergistic effects from independent contributions of each vitamin. Future research should integrate monotherapy arms with matched dosages to determine whether efficacy is mainly conferred by one vitamin or through additive or synergistic interactions.

Conclusion

The combination of vitamin D3 and vitamin E, particularly at higher doses (72 and 144 IU/kg BW of vitamin D3 with 250 mg/kg BW of vitamin E), demonstrated statistically significant improvements ($p < 0.05$) in reducing leukocyte counts, pro-inflammatory biomarkers (TNF- α , IL-6, procalcitonin, and CRP), and liver and kidney function markers (SGOT, SGPT, creatinine, and urea) in *Staphylococcus aureus*-induced sepsis in rats. These effects were comparable to the doxycycline-treated group, indicating strong immunomodulatory, hepatoprotective, and

nephroprotective properties. These preliminary findings suggest that vitamin D3 and vitamin E (α -tocopherol), particularly at higher doses, may hold potential as supplementary agents in the management of *Staphylococcus aureus*-induced sepsis. However, further well-powered studies are required to confirm these effects before clinical application can be recommended.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Approval No: 044/KEPK/UNPRI/X/2024.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Primta Bangun contributed to the conceptualization, methodology, and data collection. Gusbakti Rusip was involved in the data analysis and interpretation of results. Maya Sari Mutia and Putri Handayani contributed to the writing and critical revision of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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